

Zero-cost Abstractions To Manage Audio Resource Allocation In Functional Programming Languages

Mike Solomon

wags.fm

mike@mikesolomon.org

ABSTRACT

Audio programming languages fall into two broad categories: imperative (CSound, slang) and functional (Faust, tidal). For the latter, the declarative and immutable nature of data and control structures are often at odds with the mutable and referentially opaque nature of audio units like oscillators and filters. Recently, languages such as Rust have bridged this chasm through zero-cost abstractions that manage resource allocation in otherwise functional settings. In the same spirit, this paper presents a zero-cost abstraction for the management of audio units when working with pure audio rendering functions. The result is automatic audio memory management that incurs a minimal runtime penalty while retaining an expressive functional syntax.

1. INTRODUCTION

The prevailing resource-management paradigm in all modern DAWs and most visual or text-based music creation environments is to model resources as units that are connected to each other. This is done via patcher chords in PD and Max, busses in SuperCollider, and argument passing in CSound.

Almost all audio units preserve some notion of state internally. For example:

- Waveforms remember their previous position in a lookup table so that changes in frequency do not disrupt the phase.
- Biquad filters and delay lines need to access a certain number of input samples in the past as well as potentially their own output.
- FFT-based algorithms need to access and aggregate previous FFTs using a windowing function before rendering the output in the time domain.

Because of this, substituting one audio unit for another cannot be done in the same way that one would substitute a referentially transparent value like a floating-point number or boolean.

Copyright: © 2022 Mike Solomon et al. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

In imperative audio programming languages, such as the Web Audio API or PureData, managing stateful units is a core feature of the language. Units are assigned to variables on which arbitrary side effects, like setting a frequency or a volume, can be performed:

```
const oscillator = ctx.createOscillator();
oscillator.type = "square";
oscillator
  .frequency
  .setValueAtTime(440, ctx.currentTime);
oscillator.connect(ctx.destination);
oscillator.start();
```

However, in declarative and graph-based languages, this is more challenging. Consider, for example, the following pseudocode. It is presented in a Haskell-like syntax, and in it and the following examples, `kp` is a boolean value that answers the question “is a key currently pressed?”.

```
type KPT = { time :: Number, kp :: Boolean }
render :: KPT → AudioGraph
render { time, kp } =
  (
    if time < 5
    then sinOsc (time * 220)
    else if time < 10
    then sinOsc (time * 50)
    else highpass (playBuf "hi")
  ) `append`
  (
    when kp (sinOsc 880)
  )
```

We are now demanding much more of the audio engine:

- Even though we haven’t specified it, in almost all circumstances we will want to preserve the sine-wave oscillator across the five-second mark to avoid phase disruption.
- We do not want the engine to spuriously tear down or create new oscillators, for example arbitrarily changing oscillator units before the 10-second mark.
- We want as little runtime accounting of audio units as possible, ideally precompiling an efficient kernel to minimize how much time is spent on our control thread.

As functional frameworks such as Tidal Cycles [1] and PureScript Wags [2] become more prevalent, it is important to maintain the helpful abstraction of graphs as a pure function of time while rigorously keeping track of active and inactive audio units with as little computational overhead as possible.

This paper proposes a zero-cost abstraction to manage resource allocation in functional audio programming languages combining the following three techniques:

1. Cofree comonads [3, 4], as popularized by Edward Kmett.
2. Existential quantification [5, 6], first introduced as a programming paradigm by Nigel Perry.
3. Indexed types [7], which can be used to control transitions between states at compile time.

The paper will give examples of all three concepts, showing how they can be combined into an audio-resource management strategy. It will end by showing the results of a benchmark conducted using PureScript Wags.

2. COFREE COMONADS

The first leg of our functional journey will explore cofree comonads, which can be used as a drop-in replacement for pure functions of time in effectful settings while providing the added advantage of retaining an internal state both at the type *and* term level. It is this state that will ultimately power our zero-cost abstraction.

To understand what cofree comonads are, it is helpful to first define the following concepts in order: the functor, the comonad, and finally the cofree comonad.

2.1 Functor

A functor is a computational context into which functions can be mapped. For example, if there is a function `add1` that adds 1 to an integer, it can be mapped to the context of an array of integers `[1, 2, 3, 4]` to produce `[2, 3, 4, 5]` or to the context of a homogeneous record `{x : 1, y : 2}` to produce `{x : 2, y : 3}`. The standard definition of `map` is $\forall a\ b. (a \rightarrow b) \rightarrow m\ a \rightarrow m\ b$, mapping a function $a \rightarrow b$ to operate in context m .

Functors are ubiquitous in audio programming: for example, when we apply a function `transposeSemitone` to a sequence of notes, we understand intuitively that the transposition function is lifted into the context of the sequence even though a rhythmic sequence, pedantically speaking, cannot be “transposed” harmonically.

While functors provide a way to lift functions into contexts like arrays and records, they provide no way to extract values from those contexts, nor do they provide a way to recursively nest contexts. As we’ll see in the next section, these are bread-and-butter operations of any realtime audio rendering engine, and this is where comonads come in.

2.2 Comonad

A comonad¹ w is a functor that comes equipped with two operations that fulfill two laws.

The operations are as follows:

¹ Comonads are not to be confused with their close cousins, monads. While monads are outside the scope of this article, they are the categorical dual of comonads and can be used to model a large class of computations.

- **extract**, which extracts a value a from the term $w\ a$.
- **duplicate**, which takes a term $w\ a$ and “nests” or “projects” it into $w\ (w\ a)$.

These operations must satisfy the following laws, where e is `extract`, d is `duplicate`, and wa is an arbitrary comonad:

- $e\ (d\ (wa)) = wa$
- $map\ e\ (d\ (wa)) = wa$

The `map` in the second law is the `map` discussed previously for functors.

Even though most audio frameworks do not use comonadic terminology in their codebase, these two operations — `extract` and `duplicate` — are ubiquitous in audio programming. `extract` is the operation to get information like control-rate data or samples from a computational context.² `duplicate` is the operation that takes a context and computes its logical next iteration, which is almost always a rendering or event loop.³

Event loops have an additional unique property that is not captured by comonads - for any one iteration, they are *functorial* in nature. That is, the loop is almost never simply executed: it often exists in a computational context that furnishes it with information like the current time and external information via transports like MIDI or OSC. So, if the resultant control-rate data or sample buffer is s and the loop’s context is a functor f , then we have $w\ (f\ s)$, which is no longer a comonad of s but one of $f\ s$. To resolve this dilemma, we introduce the *cofree comonad*.

2.3 Cofree Comonad

Cofree is a data structure that is parameterized by two types: a functor f and a value a . The definition is:

```
data Cofree f a =
  Cofree a (f (Cofree f a))
```

In languages with strict evaluation, this recursive definition would cause a stack overflow, and in practice, the definition often uses a unitary thunk:

```
data Cofree f a =
  Cofree a (Unit -> f (Cofree f a))
```

The `Cofree` constructor takes two arguments: a value a and a computational context f in which one can reason about the next `Cofree f a`. Note that the next `Cofree f a` need not actually exist⁴ — event loops can enter into failure states for example, but most server-based programs (ie `scsynth`) are built around the concept of a potentially infinite event loop.

Cofree is a functor because it has the following instance for `map`:

² For example, in the SuperCollider code base, this is defined as a function called `callback` in the file `SC_AU.h`

³ For example, in the SuperCollider code base, this is defined in the file `SC_EventLoop.hpp`

⁴ For example, a functor f can choose to ignore its argument a , as is the case with ie the *Proxy* functor, <https://hackage.haskell.org/package/base-4.16.0.0/docs/Data-Proxy.html>.

```
map f (Cofree a b) =
  Cofree (f a) (map (map f) b)
```

It is a comonad because it has the following instances for extract and duplicate:

```
extract (Cofree a _) = a
duplicate c@(Cofree _ b) =
  Cofree c (map duplicate b)
```

Most importantly, Cofree can be “unwrapped” by returning the second argument:

```
unwrapCofree :: Cofree f a → f (Cofree f a)
unwrapCofree (Cofree _ b) = b
```

In an audio rendering engine, this gives us the next iteration of a rendering loop f (Cofree f a). For example, if f is (\rightarrow) Time (where Time is a positive floating-point number), then at each unwrapping of the loop, we “unlock” the next step by providing the current time. This is also called the generator pattern in imperative languages like Python and JavaScript, where `unwrapCofree` is analogous to `yield` and the f around f (Cofree f a) is discharged with the next function.

2.4 Revisiting Our Pseudocode

Let’s revisit our pseudocode through the prism of cofree comonads. We’ll reduce the size of the example for brevity:

```
type KPT = { time :: Number, kp :: Boolean }
render :: KPT → AudioGraph
render { time, kp } =
  (
    if time < 5
    then sinOsc (time * 220)
    else highpass (playBuf "hi")
  ) `append` (when kp (sinOsc 880))
```

We can rewrite this as a function that yields a cofree comonad. `extract` provides an audio graph, and `unwrapCofree` yields the next iteration of an event loop.

```
type KPT = { time :: Number, kp :: Boolean }
render :: KPT → Cofree ((→) KPT) AudioGraph
render { time, kp } =
  Cofree
    (
      (
        if time < 5
        then sinOsc (time * 220)
        else highpass (playBuf "hi")
      ) `append` (when kp (sinOsc 880))
    )
  render
```

Here, because the underlying Functor is $((\leftarrow) KPT) =$, we can use `render` recursively in its own definition.

In practice, this also changes the way an event loop is written:

```
-- with pure functions
loop = do
  time ← getTime
  kp ← ketKp
  let res = render { time, kp }
  doSomethingWith res
  delay 0.03
  loop
```

```
-- with a cofree comonad
loop =
  let f r = do
    time ← getTime
    kp ← ketKp
    let res = render { time, kp }
    doSomethingWith (extract res)
    delay 0.03
    f (unwrapCofree res)
  in f render
```

So far, this formulation provides no advantage over a pure function of time. However, things get more interesting when we introduce arbitrary internal states in the definition of our cofree comonad. For example, if we want the sine-wave oscillator to release one second after a keypress ends, there is no way to do this with a pure function of time because there is no retention of state. Cofree comonads, on the other hand, make this trivial.

```
type KPT = { time :: Number, kp :: Boolean }
render :: KPT → Cofree ((→) KPT) AudioGraph
render =
  let
    f kp_1 t_1 { time, kp } =
      Cofree
        (
          (
            if time < 5
            then sinOsc (time * 220)
            else highpass (playBuf "hi")
          ) `append`
            (when (kp || time < t_1 + 1)
              (sinOsc 880))
        )
    render kp
      (if kp_1 && not kp
        then time else t_1)
  in f false (-inf)
```

While this section has showed us how to write an event loop and how to extract k-rate/a-rate data from a computation in a functional style, it still has not solved the issue of resource management of stateful audio units. To do this, we will need to introduce the concept of existential quantification and use that to build a indexed type system within a cofree comonad.

3. EXISTENTIAL QUANTIFICATION

In the last example from Section 2, we saw how state can be carried in a cofree comonad’s definition to create effects like delayed releases of oscillators and in general any sort of memory cell needed for filtering.

This technique of propagating a term internally through a computation is called a *closure*. The terms `t_1` and `kp_1` are *lexically closed* within the environment of the cofree comonad, but are never exposed to the external computation. This technique comes with one major drawback, however: all functions that operate on the internal state need to be defined within the closure, which makes it difficult to operate on the state using external APIs.

To remedy this problem, we can use existential types. We say the type is existentially quantified, or a *coend* [8], when

a consumer of the type knows only that it exists without knowing what the type is. As an example, the `Exists` type in PureScript can be used to turn any type constructor $f a$ into an existential type $\exists a.f a$.

```
data StreamF a s = StreamF s (s → Tuple s a)
type Stream a = Exists (StreamF a)
```

One can then get into and out of the existential type using the following two functions:

```
mkExists :: forall a f. f a → Exists f
runExists
  :: forall r f
  . (forall a. f a → r)
  → Exists f
  → r
```

A useful way to think about existential types is in terms of epistemic certainty. If a universally quantified definition is true “for all” types (this is the norm in functional programming languages, for example the *identity* function is defined as $\forall a.a \rightarrow a$), then it is a tautology. On the other hand, existential types are the weakest epistemological claim one can make: they assert that something exists without knowing anything about it.

We can use existential types to transform the closure from our previous render loop into an API that exposes an internal state as type `c` to external consumers. This new type is called `WithCtrl`, and existential types are used to transform it into a cofree comonad that the rendering loop understands.

```
type WithCtrl f a c = Cofree f (a /\ c)
type Ex f a = Exists (WithCtrl f a)
type KPT = { time :: Number, kp :: Boolean }
render
  :: KPT
  → WithCtrl ((→) KPT) AudioGraph KPT
render =
  let
    f n t = Cofree
      (
        (
          (
            if n.time < 5
            then sinOsc (n.time * 220)
            else highpass (playBuf "hi")
          ) `append`
          (when (n.kp || n.time < t.time + 1)
              (sinOsc 880)) /\ t
        )
      )
    (
      render n.kp
      (
        if t.kp && not n.kp
        then n.time else t.time
      )
    )
  in f false (-inf)
```

```
asEx :: KPT → E ((→) KPT) AudioGraph
asEx = mkExists <<< render
```

```
unEx
  :: E ((→) KPT) AudioGraph
  → Cofree ((→) KPT) AudioGraph
unEx = runExists (map fst)
```

Closures and existential types are particularly useful in recursive definitions, like those of cofree comonads, because of their ability to change their internal type over the lifetime of a looping control structure. For example, a state

can be a `Number` followed by a `Boolean` followed by a `String` over the course of a computation instead of a union `Number | Boolean | String`. This significantly improves runtime performance (no pattern matching) and makes it easier to reason about programs, as non-sensical data (ie a filter’s `q` value being passed to a sine wave oscillator) is prohibited at the type level. It is also a necessary stepping stone to indexed types, which is the crux of our resource-management strategy in Section 3.

As a motivating example, let’s use a render function that switches from an oscillator and a filtered sound at the five-second mark. The behavior of the oscillator and of the filtered sound change irreversibly once a key is pressed. As a first pass, we’ll use closures to implement this behavior.

```
renderHP kp_1 fq { kp } =
  let
    isKp = kp_1 || kp
    f = fq.f + (isKp ? 0 : 1000)
    q = fq.q + (isKp ? 0 : 40)
  in Cofree
    (highpass {f: f, q: q} (playBuf "hi"))
    (render isKp fq)

renderS kp_1 f { time, kp } =
  if time > 5
  then renderHP kp_1 {f:900,q:1} {time,kp}
  else
    let
      isKp = kp_1 || kp
      f = f.f + (isKp ? 0 : 200)
    in Cofree
      (sinOsc {f: f})
      (renderS isKp fq)

render = renderS false {f: 440}
```

The types of the two internal states, `fq` and `f`, are different: one (used in `renderS`) contains frequency information for an oscillator whereas the other (used in `renderHP`) contains frequency and `q` values for a filter. And yet, they can be used inside the closure with no runtime penalty (no pattern matching) and no danger of accidentally passing information for the filter to the oscillator or vice versa.

It is possible to pass from closures to existential types by using the continuation passing pattern [9], whereby the control flow of a function (in our case, the loop) is yielded to a continuation. In the following example, for the sake of brevity, we will use monomorphic versions of the full type called `F` and of the existential type called `S`. The `AudioGraph` type is renamed `A`, and our continuation passing function is called `cp`.⁵

```
type C = {t :: Number, kp :: Boolean }
data E a b = L a | R b
data M a = J a | N
data U = U
-- F a is our type that will be existentially
-- quantified
data F a = F A a
-- S is our existential type that will erase
-- an a from (F a), leaving just the A term
data S = S (C → Tuple A S)
```

⁵Note that, in this example, lazy evaluation is assumed. In strict languages, it causes a stack overflow and the construction of the cofree comonad would need to be deferred.

```

-- continuation passing instead of a direct
-- cofree comonad constructor
cp
  :: (C → E S (F a))
  → (F a → S)
  → Scene S
cp m t = S go
  go time = case m time of
    L s → (\(S x) → x) s env
    S f@(F c a) →
      Tuple a (t f)

branch
  :: (F a → C → E S (F a))
  → F a
  → S
branch fa w = cp (fa w) (branch fa)

freeze :: F a → S
freeze s = cp (\_ → R s) freeze

-- our internal type will be the onset of
-- the keypress
frame0 { t, kp } =
  F (sinOsc 440.0) (kp ? J t : N))

loop (J t0) { t, kp } =
  F (sinOsc 440.0 + (t - t0)) (J t0)
loop N c = frame0 c

rest = highpass (playBuf "hi") /\ U

render =
  cp
    frame0
    (branch \(F _ a) c
      if t < 5
      then R (loop a c)
      else L (freeze rest)
  )

```

Now, it is possible to define functions that interact directly with the $F a$ contained by `frame0`, `loop` and `rest`, all of which contain an internal state — $M C$ in the case of `frame0` and `loop`, U in the case of `rest`. For example, to override the internal state of `frame0` to always be N , we could write `frameN = (map (F c _) → F c N) frame0`.

Furthermore, we have abstracted time management to the top-level `render` function, separating temporal branching from the definition of audio behavior. The function `cp` takes care of the type erasure from $F a$ to S in the same way that `Exists` erases a type.

As we saw with the `frameN` example above, existential types can be used both to model the type-level morphology of internal states and to write APIs for interacting with these states. It also the crucial step that allows us to reason about resource management, as we will see in the next section on indexed types.

4. INDEXED TYPES

Let's take a closer look at the definitions of $F a$ and S from the previous example. To create S , we drop both the internal type a and the term of type a . Instead, we propagate both the term and the type through the computation, allowing it to change as the computation progresses.

Nothing stops us from erasing multiple types, nor do all of the types have to appear in the corresponding terms. For example, we could have defined F as `data F i a = F A a`. Here, i is a phantom type: in addition to being erased in S , it has no representation at the term level F . We can use types like these to track aspects of our program at compile time. This is called a “zero-cost abstraction”: it is an abstraction that offloads computationally expensive algorithms like graph traversals to the compiler. At runtime, there is no performance penalty.

When phantom types are used in this way, we call them *indexed types*. Indexed types are the key to managing the allocation of resources of an audio graph using cofree comonads. Changes in indices represent changes in the underlying audio graph. For example, if index i_0 is `SinOsc` and index i_1 is `Highpass (PlayBuf)`, the compiler knows that it will have to emit instructions to destroy a sine wave oscillator and create a playable buffer linked to a highpass filter.

Let's see this technique applied to the same example above where a sine-wave oscillator changes to a filtered buffer.

```

type C = {t :: Number, kp :: Boolean }
data E a b = L a | R b
data M a = J a | N
data U = U
data F i a = F A a
data S = S (C → Tuple A S)

eg2s :: F EmptyGraph a → F SinOsc a
eg2s = unsafeCoerce

s2s :: F SinOsc a → F SinOsc a
s2s = unsafeCoerce

s2h :: F SinOsc a → F (HighPass (PlayBuf)) a
s2h = unsafeCoerce

h2h
  :: F SinOsc a
  → F (HighPass (PlayBuf)) a
h2h = unsafeCoerce

cp
  :: (C → E S (F a))
  → (F a → S)
  → Scene S
cp m t = S go
  go time = case m time of
    L s → (\(S x) → x) s env
    S f@(F c a) →
      Tuple a (t f)

branch
  :: (F a → C → E S (F a))
  → F a
  → S
branch fa w = cp (fa w) (branch fa)

freeze :: F a → S
freeze s = cp (\_ → R s) freeze

frame0 { t, kp } =
  e2s $ F (sinOsc 440.0) (kp ? J t : N))

loop (J t0) { t, kp } =
  s2s $ F (sinOsc 440.0 + (t - t0)) (J t0)

```

```

loop N c = s2s $ frame0 c

rest = highpass (playBuf "hi") /\ U

render =
  cp
    frame0
      (branch \ (F _ a) c
        if t < 5
          then R (loop a c)
          else
            L
              $ cp
                (\_ → s2h rest)
                (\_ → freeze (h2h rest))

```

This example is more complex in that there are four transitions between indexed states:

1. At time 0, a transition from the empty graph to a sine-wave oscillator (*e2s*).
2. At all remaining times until five seconds, a sine-wave oscillator to itself, meaning a no-op (*s2s*).
3. At the five-second mark, transition from a sine-wave oscillator to a filtered buffer (*s2h*).
4. From here until the audio is shut off (*h2h*).

On the term level, these transitions are no-ops that are tracked entirely at compile-time, which speeds up audio rendering. Instead, the only changes that need to be propagated to the graph are new control values, which requires no diffing between graphs. Furthermore, the use of control structures like *sinOsc* and *playBuf* can be verified against their type-level counterparts so that control data for an oscillator is never allowable when an oscillator is not in the type-level graph, etc.

For several examples of this technique being used in actual audio computations, one may consult the example folder of the *purescript-wags* project⁶.

Before looking at benchmarks in the next section, let's revisit the path to indexed types to show how the allocation of audio resources can be tracked by indices in a purely functional setting.

1. Instead of repeatedly calling a pure function of time, rendering loops can unfold a cofree comonad that yields functions of time at each iteration. This is also called a Moore machine.
2. Cofree comonads can have changing internal states, and these states can be represented at the type-level as multivariate type constructors that are transformed into cofree comonads via existential quantification.
3. One of these existentially-eliminated types can be an index that tracks the current state of the audio graph. The compiler, as it tracks the evolution of this type, can emit efficient instructions for graph manipulations at compile-time, eliminating the need for runtime graph traversals.

⁶ <https://github.com/mikesol/purescript-wags/tree/main/examples/kitchen-sink>

Figure 1. The rendering result of an audio graph created using zero-cost abstractions at compile-time.

Figure 2. The rendering result of an audio graph created using runtime graph traversals.

5. EXAMPLE AND BENCHMARK

To illustrate the runtime benefits of this approach, the following test was run.

1. An audio graph with 61 units - 1 speaker, 30 gain controls and 30 sine-wave oscillators, was created twice using the Google Chrome implementation of the Web Audio API. Both versions model an audio graph as a pure function of time.⁷
 - 1.1. The first version⁸ uses the zero-cost abstraction described in this paper.
 - 1.2. The second version⁹ uses a runtime graph traversal to detect changes in the graph.
2. Approximately ten seconds of audio was rendered using the both versions.
3. The results are as follows:
 - 3.1. The first version's audio rendering took approximately 1.7% of the total rendering time. This is shown in Figure 1.
 - 3.2. The first version's audio rendering took 38.8% of the total rendering time. This is shown in Figure 2.

This shows that, for a moderately complex audio graph, the zero-cost abstraction was over 22 times faster than the version that made runtime graph traversals. This result can be reproduced at the following url: <https://smc2022.surge.sh>.

⁷ The function can be seen at the following URL: <https://github.com/mikesol/purescript-wags/blob/b6930c5aab6ec5f04f7d8d07231a04b12f70388e/examples/smc2022/SMC2022.purs#L39>.

⁸ See this url: <https://github.com/mikesol/purescript-wags/blob/b6930c5aab6ec5f04f7d8d07231a04b12f70388e/examples/smc2022/SMC2022.purs#L74>.

⁹ See this url: <https://github.com/mikesol/purescript-wags/blob/b6930c5aab6ec5f04f7d8d07231a04b12f70388e/examples/smc2022/SMC2022.purs#L77>.

6. CONCLUSION

As functional audio programming becomes more ubiquitous and as large media houses like Epic Games¹⁰ turn to functional programming to power parts of their rendering pipelines, the need for efficient representations of purely functional audio graphs becomes increasingly important. This paper presents a zero-cost abstraction for managing audio units by using existential typing to erase indexed representations of audio graphs in a cofree comonad. The resulting algorithm was able to outperform a runtime graph traversal by a factor of 22 on a moderately complex graph. While the algorithm was presented in Haskell-family pseudocode, the technique can be applied to any language that can perform type-level functions on partially-applied types, as `Exists` does in this paper (Scala, F#, PureScript, Agda, and Idris all have this feature, for example). By following this method, artists can benefit from the conceptual elegance and power of the functional style while enjoying the fast runtime behavior traditionally associated with imperative languages.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] “Tidal cycles.” [Online]. Available: <https://tidalcycles.org/>
- [2] “Wags documentation.” [Online]. Available: <https://docs.wags.fm/>
- [3] “free: Monads for free,” <https://hackage.haskell.org/package/free-5.1.7>, accessed: 2022-01-12.
- [4] P. Freeman, “Declarative uis are the future—and the future is comonadic!” 2017.
- [5] N. Perry, “The implementation of practical functional programming languages,” Ph.D. dissertation, Citeseer, 1991.
- [6] K. Läufer and M. Odersky, “Polymorphic type inference and abstract data types,” *ACM Transactions on Programming Languages and Systems (TOPLAS)*, vol. 16, no. 5, pp. 1411–1430, 1994.
- [7] C. Zenger, “Indexed types,” *Theoretical computer science*, vol. 187, no. 1-2, pp. 147–165, 1997.
- [8] N. Yoneda, “On ext and exact sequences,” *J. Fac. Sci. Univ. Tokyo Sect. I*, vol. 8, no. 507-576, p. 1960, 1960.
- [9] G. J. Sussman and G. L. Steele Jr, “Ai memo no. 349 december 1975,” *contract*, vol. 14, no. 75-C, p. 0643.

¹⁰ See <https://discourse.haskell.org/t/an-epic-future-for-spj/3573>